

Studies on adsorption mechanism of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} onto polymeric resins

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The determination of low level of metal ions in environmental samples and their selective separation from wastewater by using commercially available polymeric resins is the most prominent one due to their favorable stability and structural diversity that allow to modulate their adsorption capacity and selectivity. In this study, we have attempted to elucidate the adsorption mechanism of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} onto the polymeric resins by corroborating the experimental observations with theoretical results. It was found that electrostatic interaction and chemisorption involving C=O group were the major mechanisms for adsorption of the metal ions onto Amberlite XAD-7 and Diaion HP-2MG. Adsorption onto Amberlite XAD-4 was mainly due to the participation C=C group present on the adsorbent surface. FTIR analysis supported the participation of C=O and C=C groups during Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} adsorption.

Keywords: Adsorption affinity, adsorption enthalpy, Amberlite XAD-7, interaction energy, heavy metal ions.

Introduction

A Balanced ecosystem is necessary for the survival of human and other organisms. Developing technology seems to have an adverse effect on our ecosystem. Heavy metal pollution is one of the main problems due to its toxic effects and accumulation throughout the food chain, which is becoming the main threats to human health. The industrial effluents from metal industry, mainly electroplating and surface finishing plants produce enormous amounts of wastewaters containing heavy metal ions^{1,2} polluting the surface as well as groundwater. Also the effluents from electronic industry and recycling plants for spent electronic devices contain very hazardous ions of heavy metals². Industrial wastes from these industries contaminate the environment, among which Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn, Pb and Cd metal ions appear predominantly. Moreover, Cd, Cu, Ni and Co are included on the US Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) list of priority pollutants³. Therefore, it is necessary to remove or minimize the heavy metal ions from wastewater systematically prior to its discharge to the environment.

Although various methods for the metal removal and recovery have been developed, adsorption is considered as an effective separation process for removal of heavy metal from wastewater⁴. Recently, particular focus is given to innovative physico-chemical removal processes like adsorp-

tion on new adsorbents^{4,5}. Despite the development of naturally derived low-cost materials, new adsorbents have been developed from commercially available macroreticular polymeric resins⁶⁻⁹. Macroporous resins have been widely used for the removal of heavy metals from metal-contaminated wastewater and can be easily regenerated using appropriate elution solvent. Because of high efficiency, procedural simplicity, stability and structural diversity, macroporous resins are suitable for industrial applications. Amberlite XAD-7 is a suitable adsorbent for quantitative retention in preconcentration¹⁰. Impregnated Amberlite XAD-7 acted as effective adsorbents for removal of Cr^{III}, Cr^{VI} and other metal ions from aqueous solutions¹¹⁻¹⁴. Amberlite XAD-4 and modified amberlite XAD-4 had been effectively as adsorbents for selective separation of metal ions¹⁵. Raganati *et al.*¹⁶ have used Amberlite XAD-7 and XAD-4 for selective adsorption of butanol from acetone-butanol-ethanol fermentation broth. Amberlite XAD-7 and XAD-4 have been also used for removal of organics such as salicylic, gallic acids, lactic acid and levulinic acid from aqueous solutions¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Modified Diaion HP-2MG is used as adsorbent for solid phase extraction and flame atomic absorption spectrometric determination of metal ions²⁰. Heavy metals at trace levels have been separated and preconcentrated using *Anoxybacillus gonensis* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* immobilized on Diaion HP-2MG as bioadsorbents^{21,22}.

In the present paper, both theoretical and experimental results are reported for adsorption of certain heavy metals such as Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with three commercially available structurally dissimilar polymeric sorbents. Although several experimental studies have been reported on adsorptive separation process for removal of heavy metal ions, however there has been relatively less theoretical study on the mechanism. We hope this study will be useful for deducing implication in design and development of appropriate adsorbent for effective removal of heavy metals from industrial wastewater.

Experimental

Materials and analytical techniques:

Analytical grade Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were obtained from Merck and used without further purification. The reagents used as buffer (sodium phosphate, sodium acetate, sodium carbonate and sodium chloride) were supplied by Qualigens, India (Mumbai) and were of analytical grade. The polymeric resins such as Amberlite XAD-4, Amberlite XAD-7 and Diaion HP-2MG were obtained from Sigma Chemical Co., USA. The adsorbents were washed with deionized water and dried overnight before use. The concentrations of heavy metal ion solutions were measured by atomic absorption spectrophotometry using a Perkin-Elmer 3030 instrument. FTIR spectra were obtained by the KBr method (Perkin-Elmer, model Spectrum One).

Adsorption measurements:

Equilibrium isotherms were obtained by contacting 25 ml of aqueous metal ion solution with different amounts of

using an atomic adsorption spectrometer. The adsorbents used were Amberlite XAD-4, XAD-7 and Diaion-HP-2MG. The chemical and physical properties of these polymeric resins are given in Table 1. The amounts of metal ions per gram of adsorbent q (mmol g⁻¹) was calculated as $q = V \times (C - C_e) / W$, where C and C_e are the initial and equilibrium solute concentrations (mmol L⁻¹), V is the solution volume (L) and W is the weight of the adsorbent (g). All the experiments were carried out in triplicate and the reproducibility was found to be $\pm 2\%$. Experiments on adsorption rate were conducted in a stirred constant volume vessel similar to that used in our previous works^{23,24}. The liquid volume was 100 cm³ with 3–3.5 g of adsorbent sample. The initial concentration of metal ion was taken between 10 and 15 mM at 25 \pm 0.5°C. The liquid volume was monitored at equal time intervals till equilibration.

Adsorptive interaction in aqueous solutions:

The interaction energy between the metal ions and polymeric adsorbents (Fig. 1) were calculated using Density functional theory (DFT). Calculations were performed employing B3LYP exchange-correlation functional and the 6-31G** standard basis set available in Gaussian 09 package²⁵. The adsorption energy, ΔE_{ads} of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with adsorbents given in Table 2 was calculated using eq. (1)²⁶. The optimized geometry of Cu-XAD-7 and Ni-XAD-7 system are shown in Fig. 2 (a and b). For optimized geometries of other systems such as Cu/Ni-HP-2MG and Cu/Ni-XAD-4, Please see Figs. S1 and S2. Selective data such as bond distance, bond angles, infrared (IR) frequencies are given in Table 3.

Table 1. Chemical and physical properties of resins reported by manufacturers

Trade name	Matrix	Surface area (m ² /g)	Pore radius (Å)	Wet mesh size	Particle size (mm)
Amberlite XAD-7	Acrylic ester	450	45	20–60	0.25–0.84
Amberlite XAD-4	Styrene-divinyl benzene	725	20	20–60	0.25–0.84
Diaion HP-2MG	Acrylic ester	500	85	20–60	0.3–0.6

adsorbents in a thermostated shaker bath controlled at 25 \pm 0.5°C. The initial concentration of metal ion in the aqueous solution was varied between 8 and 20 mM. The equilibration time was 4–5 h. After equilibrium was achieved, the mixture was allowed to settle and the supernatant liquor was filtered to remove any particulate matter. The concentrations of the metal ion before and after adsorption were determined

Fig. 1. Structural molecular model of adsorbent surfaces.

Table 2. Adsorption energy and thermodynamic parameters of the metal-adsorbent system

Adsorbate	Adsorbent	Adsorption affinity q/C_e (L g ⁻¹)	Adsorption enthalpy ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Interaction energy ΔE_{ads} (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Entropy ΔS (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)
Cu ^{II}	XAD-7	0.723	-19.804	-201	-68.523
	HP-2MG	0.459	-18.465	-177	-67.168
	XAD-4	0.186	-10.833	-072	-49.654
Ni ^{II}	XAD-7	0.363	-17.625	-150	-66.196
	HP-2MG	0.251	-16.794	-138	-67.426
	XAD-4	0.104	-07.723	-069	-44.097

Fig. 2. Optimized geometry of (a) Cu-XAD-7 and (b) Ni-XAD-7 system.

$$\Delta E_{\text{ads}} = E_{\text{system}} - (E_{\text{adsorbate}} + E_{\text{adsorbent}}) \quad (1)$$

where E_{system} , $E_{\text{adsorbate}}$ and $E_{\text{adsorbent}}$ represent HF energies (heats of formation) of the metal-adsorbent system, the free metal and the adsorbent, respectively.

Results and discussion

Adsorption equilibrium:

The adsorption isotherms for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} on different

Table 3. Selective data of bond distances, bond angles, IR frequencies of the metal (M)-adsorbent system

	C=O (Å)	C=C (Å)	O-M (Å)	OMO angle (°)	IR freq. C=O (cm ⁻¹)
XAD-7	1.2450	–	–	–	1676.38
Cu-XAD-7	1.2847	–	1.856	106.59	1401.18
Ni-XAD-7	1.2809	–	1.918	91.68	1566.27
HP-2MG	1.2502	–	–	–	1762.74
Cu-HP-2MG	1.2624	–	1.724	–	1615.52
Ni-HP-2MG	1.2613	–	1.821	–	1620.25
XAD-4	–	1.398	–	–	1667.19
Cu-XAD-4	–	1.428	–	–	1600.34
Ni-XAD-4	–	1.418	–	–	1628.08

adsorbents are shown in Fig. 3 (a and b). The adsorption equilibria were interpreted from Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms. Table 4 shows the values of the isotherm parameters estimated by non-linear regression analysis. It appears that Freundlich model provided the most satisfactory representation of the data at almost all the pH values studied with correlation values close to one. The Freundlich model was found to agree well with experimental data for adsorption of heavy metal ions on carbon nanotubes²⁷ and adsorptive removal of Cu^{II} ions onto 4-ethyl thiosemicarbazide intercalated organophilic calcined hydrotalcite²⁸. It can be seen from Table 4 that $1/n$ values were below 1, which signified high adsorption capacity and the value approaching 0, indicated that the surface becoming more heterogeneous^{29,30}. Experimentally obtained adsorption equilibria were characterized in terms of the affinities (q/C_e), which is defined as the equilibrium ratio of the solid-phase concentration (mmol g⁻¹ sorbent) to the liquid-phase solute concentration (mmol L⁻¹).

As will be discussed, the adsorption affinity has been used in our studies as a measure of the adsorption equilibrium.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3. The adsorption isotherms for (a) Cu^{II} and (b) Ni^{II} on different adsorbents. Closed, open and crossed for pH 5, 4 and 3 respectively.

The adsorption affinities for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} at pH 5 are reported in Table 2. The pH dependence of adsorption is of importance as it determines the oxidation state of metal ions, thereby affecting the adsorption affinity. Also, pH has an effect on the surface binding sites of the polymeric adsorbents, and hence it induces different interaction between the adsorbent and adsorbate. Fig. 4 (a and b) shows the variation of q/C_e with pH and inferred a strong relationship, the affinity being considerably high with increasing pH. Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions almost exist in +2 oxidation state at pH between 2 and 6³¹. At lower pH, the adsorption affinity was less as H^+ ions and metal ions competed for the same adsorption sites and thus reduced the possibility of metal ion adsorption. At higher pH, the concentration of H^+ ions decreases and the decrease in positive charge of the adsorbent increased adsorption affinity. Also at higher pH, the negative charge on the surface of

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Adsorption affinity vs pH of various resins: (a) Cu^{II} and (b) Ni^{II} .

the adsorbents facilitated electrostatic interaction which favored adsorption of metal ions.

The greater adsorption affinity of Cu^{II} compared to Ni^{II} for all the adsorbents studied here may be governed by the strength of stability constants between the metal ions and surface functional groups. It is reported in the literature³² that Cu^{II} has higher stability constant than Ni^{II} and therefore, it is believed that Cu^{II} interacted stronger with surface -C=O groups of XAD-7 and HP-2MG than Ni^{II} . Theoretically, we have found that Cu-O bond lengths in Cu-XAD-7, HP-2MG is shorter than those of Ni-O bonds in Ni-XAD-7, HP-2MG, which indicated stronger interaction of Cu compared to Ni with these adsorbents. The selective data such as bond lengths, bond angles and IR frequencies for Cu-XAD-7, Ni-XAD-7, Cu-HP-2MG, Ni-HP-2MG, Cu-XAD-4 and Ni-XAD-4

Table 4. Parameter values for the adsorption isotherms of metal ions at 25°C

System	pH	Langmuir model			Freundlich model		
		$q_e = K_L X_m C_e / (1 + K_L C_e)$			$q_e = K_f C_e^n$		
		K_L	X_m	R^2	K_f	n	R^2
Cu-XAD-7	3	6.349	5.334	0.9988	3.285	8.573	0.9990
	4	4.679	1.016	0.9988	4.681	8.870	0.9991
	5	6.276	9.217	0.9893	5.674	8.517	0.9994
Cu-HP-2MG	3	2.691	8.709	0.9945	2.224	9.714	0.9950
	4	1.338	2.560	0.9910	3.180	7.423	0.9940
	5	1.071	3.841	0.9986	3.886	7.853	0.9993
Cu-XAD-4	3	1.512	7.021	0.9964	1.011	9.929	0.9967
	4	2.599	5.740	0.9945	1.413	9.677	0.9948
	5	4.218	4.530	0.9921	1.874	8.983	0.9923
Ni-XAD-7	3	2.658	8.652	0.9941	1.889	6.168	0.9961
	4	1.402	1.480	0.9939	1.948	7.171	0.9970
	5	8.256	2.948	0.9975	2.377	8.060	0.9984
Ni-HP-2MG	3	1.394	1.323	0.9956	1.446	7.388	0.9978
	4	1.666	1.160	0.9941	1.747	6.981	0.9965
	5	7.488	2.378	0.9943	1.777	8.076	0.9972
Ni-XAD-4	3	1.188	4.879	0.9362	4.927	1.073	0.9989
	4	1.522	4.415	0.9169	6.136	1.017	0.9979
	5	9.089	1.075	0.9878	6.198	1.218	0.9987

are listed in Table 3. As it can be seen from Table 3 that C=O bond lengths of XAD-7 and HP-2MG have increased after adsorption of Cu and Ni with concomitant decrease of respective Cu/Ni-O bonds. Whereas for XAD-4 the C=C bond lengths have increased with decrease of Cu/Ni-C bonds. The differences in adsorption will further be clear from FTIR spectroscopic studies and discussions on the adsorption enthalpy and energy to follow.

Adsorption kinetics:

In order to get insights into the mechanism of adsorption, adsorption rate curves generated at a stirring speed of 800 rpm (Fig. 5) were fitted to pseudo-first and pseudo-second order kinetic models. Both the equations are based on the adsorption of an adsorbate from a solution onto solid adsorbents³³.

The pseudo-first order or Lagergren equation is:

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \left(\frac{K_1}{2.303} \right) t \quad (2)$$

where q_e and q are the amounts of metal ion adsorbed (mmol g⁻¹) at equilibrium and time (t), respectively and K_1 (min⁻¹) is the pseudo-first order rate constant or adsorption rate con-

stant. The linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ versus (Fig. 5(a)) are used to determine K_1 .

The linearized form of the pseudo-second order equation is given below

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \left(\frac{1}{q_e} \right) t \quad (3)$$

The values of q_e and K_2 were estimated from the slope and the intercept of the plot $\left(\frac{t}{q_t} \right)$ versus t (Fig. 5(b)). The corresponding kinetic parameters from both the models are listed in Table 5. As can be observed, pseudo-second order equation provided a better representation of the experimental data compared to the first order equation. The pseudo-second order kinetic model was found to be applicable for adsorption of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} on sphagnum moss peat³⁴. If the second order equation is applicable, the adsorption process was subjected to a second order rate law with respect to the availability of adsorption sites on the surface of adsorbent rather than adsorbate concentration in bulk solution³⁵. The agreement of the experimental data with the second order equation indicated that the adsorption of heavy metals onto the

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Pseudo-first order (a) and second order (b) plot for adsorption of metal ions on polymeric resins. Open and closed symbols for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively.

polymeric resins was controlled by chemisorption involving valence forces between adsorbate and adsorbent^{33,36}.

The availability of adsorption sites on the surface at time t can be expressed by

$$\lambda = 1 - \frac{q_t}{q_e} \quad (4)$$

For a virgin adsorbent the value of λ equals 1, and decreases to zero when the adsorption reaction reaches its equilibrium under given experimental conditions. A better understanding of the molecular orientation of adsorbed metal ion and the extent of adsorbent surface area occupied will be needed to accurately relate these results to availability of adsorption sites.

Correlation of adsorptive affinity with interaction energy:

The adsorption affinity of XAD-7 was higher than that exhibited by HP-2MG and XAD-4 for both the metal ions studied in this work as can be seen from Table 2. Usually adsorption is affected by external physicochemical parameters such as pH, temperature, concentration, competing compounds present in solution and on the chemical structure and other characteristic properties of the adsorbent such as particle size, porosity, polarity, specific surface area, and pore volume distribution. However, these parameters have not been explicitly considered for the interpretation of the correlation between adsorption affinity and interaction energy. Adsorptive interaction energy calculated using DFT has the potential for providing a more detailed understanding of metal-polymeric resin adsorption reactions.

The adsorptive interaction energy ΔE , calculated by using eq. (1), inferred a unique relationship with adsorptive affinity for the two metal ions tested. The adsorbent which showed highest affinity, also showed the highest interaction energy (Table 2), i.e. ΔE_{ads} . Similarly, the adsorbent exhibiting the lowest affinity also showed the lowest interaction energy implying that sorbent surface chemistry affected the

Table 5. Kinetic parameters for adsorption of metal ions onto polymeric resins

Adsorbate	Adsorbent	Pseudo-first order		Pseudo-second order		
		K_1 (min ⁻¹)	R^2	K_2 (mmol g ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	q_e	R^2
Cu ^{II}	XAD-7	0.075	0.971	0.744	0.342	0.997
	HP-2MG	0.066	0.955	0.165	0.559	0.993
	XAD-4	0.092	0.935	0.061	0.599	0.991
Ni ^{II}	XAD-7	0.082	0.943	0.060	0.746	0.993
	HP-2MG	0.066	0.978	0.027	0.852	0.990
	XAD-4	0.069	0.954	0.025	0.645	0.989

adsorption equilibrium of metal ions on polymeric resins. The values of ΔE_{ads} indicated that chemisorptions might have played some role in the adsorption processes of metal ions on XAD-7 and HP-2MG and was possibly through complexation with oxygen atoms and -C=O functional groups on the surfaces. The adsorption of metal ions on XAD-4 is attributed to the metal- π interaction, which is a noncovalent interaction between an electron rich π -system and a positively charged metal ion and this interaction is as strong or stronger than H-bonding in some contexts³⁷.

Correlation adsorption enthalpy with interaction energy:

The effect of temperature on adsorption equilibrium was evaluated by measuring the adsorption at three different temperatures, i.e. 25, 40 and 55°C and at a constant pH value of 5. van't Hoff method utilizing the temperature dependence of the adsorption affinity, q/C_e (C_e being the equilibrium solute concentration) as reported in our earlier work^{38,39} has been adopted to estimate the adsorption enthalpy.

The first thermodynamic relationship being:

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K = -RT \left(\frac{q}{C_e} \right) \quad (5)$$

where ΔG° is the standard free energy of adsorption, R is the universal gas constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin and K is the equilibrium constant for the adsorption process. By confining our studies to low solute concentration, adsorption was limited to the linear region of the isotherm, and therefore we believe that the equilibrium constant can be directly related to the adsorption affinity⁴⁰.

The second thermodynamic relationship used in the van't Hoff method is:

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (6)$$

where ΔH° and ΔS° are the standard enthalpy and entropy changes of adsorption, respectively.

Combining the above equations, we have:

$$\ln \left(\frac{q}{C_e} \right) = -\frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 6 shows the van't Hoff plots of $\ln \left(\frac{q}{C_e} \right)$ versus $1/T$ and the values of ΔH° and ΔS° were determined from slopes and intercepts, respectively. The corresponding values of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 2. It can be observed from Table 2 that the adsorbent giving highest ad-

Fig. 6. Typical van't Hoff plot for adsorption of (a) Cu^{II} and (b) Ni^{II} on polymeric resins.

sorption enthalpy (ΔH) values also gave highest adsorptive interaction energy (ΔE), which increases in the order: XAD-7 > HP-2MG > XAD-4. This implies that the enthalpies of adsorption are in conformity with adsorptive interaction energy. Since the enthalpy is a measure of the strength of the solute-sorbent binding interaction, the results demonstrated that the strength of the solute-sorbent binding interaction significantly affected the adsorption affinity, contributing the full enthalpic factor to the overall process.

Moreover, the negative values of ΔH° supported that the adsorption of metal ions on polymeric resins was exothermic in nature and hence with increasing temperature the adsorbed amount at equilibrium decreased. Similar results have been obtained for heavy metal adsorption on cellulosic fibres modified by beta-cyclodextrin⁴¹. The energy released during the adsorption process compensated for the entropy loss of metal ions on the active sites of the adsorbent.

FTIR spectroscopic study:

FTIR studies have been done to gain information regarding the surface groups that might have participated in the adsorption reaction and also indicates the surface sites on which adsorption have taken place. Fig. 7 shows the FTIR spectra of XAD-7 before and after adsorption of Cu^{II}. The spectrum of XAD-7 showed a sharp band at 1737 cm⁻¹, which represented C=O stretching vibrations of the ester group. The shift in peak position to lower frequency 1573 cm⁻¹ after adsorption (Cu), indicated that the carbonyl groups might directly be involved in interaction with metal to form surface complexes. The Computational IR spectrum of XAD-7 showed a sharp band at 1676.38 cm⁻¹ for C=O stretching

vibration (Fig. S3). In Cu-XAD-7 (Fig. S4), Ni-XAD-7 (Fig. S5), the theoretical IR frequency red shifted to 1401.18 cm⁻¹ and 1566.27 cm⁻¹, respectively. The red shift of C=O frequency is more for Cu-XAD-7 compared to Ni-XAD-7, referring stronger π back bonding of Cu-C=O bond compared to Ni-C=O⁴². This stronger π bonding modulates strength and bond length of M(metal)-O bonds (Table 3). Whenever π back bonding increase, the bond length of M-O bond decreases with concomitant increase of C=O bond length⁴³. This lengthening of C=O bonds in Cu/Ni-XAD-7 is consistent with red shifting of the C=O vibrational frequencies⁴⁴. Such large shift to lower frequency indicated that the C=O groups of XAD-7 bind to the metal using "synergistic π " back bonding, where

Fig. 7. FTIR spectra of XAD-7 before (a) and after (b) Cu^{II} adsorption.

CO donates electrons to the metal's center from its HOMO and the metal center donates electrons through a d orbital to π^* antibonding orbitals of CO's LUMO. The peak at 1738 cm^{-1} in the spectra of HP-2MG is also attributable to C=O stretching vibrations of the ester group (Fig. S6). The decrease in intensity of the corresponding peak in the spectra of HP-2MG after adsorption of Cu^{II} (Fig. S7) indicated that C=O functional groups were involved in interaction with metal during the process. Although experimentally we observed intensity change and only slight shift of C=O frequency for HP-2MG after adsorption of Cu^{II}, we have observed significant shift in C=O frequency from Computational IR spectra. In the Computational IR spectrum of HP-2MG (Fig. S8), the band at 1762.74 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to C=O group had shifted to 1615.52 and 1620.25 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II}-HP-2MG (Fig. S9) and Ni^{II}-HP-2MG (Fig. S10), respectively. Therefore, like XAD-7, in HP-2MG also C=O group contributed to the binding of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}. From these observations it can be inferred that though structurally similar, XAD-7 interacted stronger with both the metal ions than that of HP-2MG. The Computational IR spectrum of XAD-4 (Fig. S11) shows a peak at 1667.19 cm^{-1} , which might correspond to C=C stretching of the aromatic group of XAD-4. The observation from IR study showed that C=C peak shifted to frequency 1600.34 cm^{-1} (Fig. S12) and 1628.08 cm^{-1} (Fig. S13) after interaction with Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}, respectively. It can be inferred that the metal ion forms a sigma bond through s orbitals and π back bonding arises through metal d orbital to π^* orbital of C=C

double bond. This clearly indicates the involvement of C=C moiety of XAD-4 in the adsorption of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II} ions^{45,46}.

Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the adsorption of metal ions onto XAD-7 and HP-2MG surfaces were partially due to the formation of metal-carbonyl bond and onto XAD-4 were due to metal π interaction.

Adsorption mechanism:

The results showed that adsorption of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} occurred on moderate polar (XAD-7/HP-2MG) and non-polar (XAD-4) adsorbents to different extent. The extent of adsorption related to the solution pH, the availability of adsorption sites on the surface adsorbent surface and the chemistry of metal ions-adsorbent interactions. The adsorption was also governed by the value of stability constants of the metal ions. The strength of the stability constant of metal ions and surface functional groups were successfully used to predict the adsorption selectivity Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} on modified polymer microbeads⁴⁷ and mesoporous silica⁴⁸. The energy of adsorption from different forces were measured by Oopen *et al.*⁴⁹ as van der Waals forces 4–10 kJ mol^{-1} , hydrophobic bond forces about 5 kJ mol^{-1} , hydrogen bond forces 2–40 kJ mol^{-1} , coordination exchange about 40 kJ mol^{-1} , dipole bond forces 2–29 kJ mol^{-1} , and chemical bond forces >60 kJ mol^{-1} . In our study, the energy of adsorption calculated by DFT method and the enthalpy of adsorption were found to be in the ranges 69–201 kJ mol^{-1} and 7.72 to –19.80 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively. Our theoretical results can be used as a complement to experimental observations for providing the mecha-

Table 6. A comparative study on adsorption behavior of based on the studied resins

System	Adsorption behaviour	Reference
Cu ^{III} - Impregnated XAD-7	The adsorption of Cr ^{III} followed second order kinetic model and the equilibrium data fitted Langmuir isotherm model. Physical as well as chemical reaction or ion exchange attributed to the adsorption process.	11
Cr ^{VI} - Impregnated XAD-7	The adsorption process was governed by pseudo-second order kinetics. And intraparticle diffusion was the rate controlling step.	50
Copper ions- Impregnated XAD-7	The adsorption mechanism was controlled by pseudo-second order kinetics. Both Langmuir and Freundlich models described the adsorption process.	13
Heavy metal- Anoxybacillusgonensis immobilized Diaion HP-2MG	Bioadsorption had been reported for separation of trace heavy metals. Optimum pH was reported to be 6 for Zn, Fe, Pb and Cu, and 8 for Cd and Co.	17
Cr ^{VI} -solvent Impregnated Diaion HP-2MG	The adsorption process followed Langmuir kind behaviour and kinetics was found to be diffused controlled.	51

nism of binding involved in metal ion adsorption onto polymeric surfaces. The selective adsorption of these two metal ions onto XAD-7 and HP-2MG might be attributed to electrostatic interactions of the adsorbent with the charged metal cations and chemical interactions due to the donation of electrons from the σ orbital of CO to the cation, and back-donation from d orbitals of the cation to the π^* orbital of CO. Thus the observed C=O frequency shifts in Cu/Ni-XAD-7 and Cu/Ni-HP-2MG is a balance among the three different bonding contribution^{43,44}. The theoretical IR spectra of Cu/Ni-XAD-4 demonstrated the involvement of C=C during adsorption supporting the (metal pi interaction) during adsorption. A comparative study on adsorption and separation behaviour of metal ions onto the resins reported in this work is given Table 6.

Conclusion

Adsorption interaction energies between heavy metal ions (Cu and Ni) and three different adsorbents such as Amberlite XAD-4, XAD-7 and Diaion HP-2MG were calculated using density functional theory. Our theoretical results are in good explanation for experimental results on adsorption affinity and enthalpy. The selective adsorption of these two metal ions onto XAD-7 can be ascribed to "synergistic π " back bonding because of the presence of -C=O groups in the structure of the adsorbents. The adsorption of these two metal ions onto XAD-4 surface was mainly due to cation- π interaction involving π -electrons on the adsorbent surface. The Freundlich model being found to provide better fit of the experimental data and indicated that the adsorbent surface becoming more heterogeneous with a spectrum of binding energies. The results of this study are expected to provide implications to design alternative adsorbents which exhibit high selectivity and affinity for adsorption of heavy by limiting adsorption to specific interactions.

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